

ALEXANDRU IOAN CUZA
UNIVERSITY of IAȘI

Train the Teachers Toolkit

*Global Citizenship and Diversity Management Skills
in Higher Education*

2021-1-LT01-KA220-HED-000023530

GLOBDIVES

Funded by the
European Union

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UNIVERSITY of IAȘI

Train the Teachers Toolkit

for raising awareness about diversity and inclusion in teaching practices & for teaching in a diverse academic environment

GLOBDIVES PROJECT

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Content

Glossary of terms - p.4

Brief project presentation - p.7

Context for TTT development -p.12

- 1. Diversity and inclusion competencies for higher education teachers - p.16**
 - 1.1. General aspects on higher education teachers' competencies - p.17
 - 1.2. Literature review on diversity management and inclusion in teaching in partner countries - p.20
 - 1.3. Research on diversity management and inclusion competencies in partner universities - p.51
- 2. Introducing diversity and inclusion into curriculum - p. 58**
 - 2.1. Importance of addressing diversity and inclusion topics - p. 59
 - 2.2. General pedagogical recommendations - p. 62
 - 2.3. How to integrate diversity topic in SSHA and BA fields – some examples – p. 67
 - 2.4. Raising awareness on diversity and inclusion importance in STEM - p. 71
- 3. Managing a diverse classroom in higher education - p. 75**
 - 3.1. Higher education teachers' awareness on diverse classroom - p. 79
 - 3.2. Strategies for teaching international students to boost inclusivity – p. 102
 - 3.3. Learning styles and teaching styles - p. 107
 - 3.4. Challenging scenarios and their solutions for teaching and guiding diverse students – p. 113

Further readings – p. 120

References - p. 123

Glossary of terms

- Competence: the ability to apply learning outcomes adequately in a defined context (education, work, personal or professional development), to use knowledge, skills and personal, social and/or methodological abilities, in work or study situations and in professional and personal development.
- Culture: The programming of the human mind by which one group of people distinguishes itself from another group. (Hofstede - <https://news.hofstede-insights.com/news/what-do-we-mean-by-culture>, retrieved October 2023)
- Diversity refers to 'cultural, linguistic, ethnic, developmental and other aspects of human difference that represent' elements of identity characterising 'both individuals and groups and accounting for 'differences between people' (Florian and Pantić, 2017, p. 1).
- Diversity layers: there are various dimensions of diversity that could be divided into 4 layers of diversity: (1) personality, that can be also broken down in different dimensions; (2) internal dimensions – e.g. age, gender identity, sexual orientation, physical ability, ethnicity, race; (3) external dimensions – e.g. geographic location, income, religion, educational background, work experience; (4) organizational dimensions – e.g. functional level, department/unit, seniority, union affiliation (Gardenswartz and Rowe, 2003)

Glossary of terms

Inclusion: the practice of providing equal access to opportunities and resources for people who might otherwise be excluded or marginalized (Oxford Dictionary).

Competence development for inclusion is underpinned by the core values of equity and inclusion. It reflects the ethical notion of true engagement and responsibility for others, while keeping in mind the holistic view of competences and the many expressions of inclusive practice found in diverse contexts (Allan, 2011; Caena, 2014; European Agency, 2019).

Glossary of terms

TPL = Teacher Professional Learning

TPL continuum refers to the whole range of TPL opportunities throughout a teacher's career, including initial teacher education (ITE), induction, continuing professional development (CPD), and professional learning opportunities for teacher educators.

TPL for inclusion: reflective practice and personal competence development of all teachers, specialists and support staff, in the areas of valuing learners' differences, learner support and working with others. This definition is in line with the Agency's Profile of Inclusive Teachers (European Agency, 2012).

TPL for inclusion policy refers to the development and implementation of legislation, regulations and other policy aspirations and actions to enhance and support TPL for inclusion, in order to prepare all teachers to include all learners.

Source: https://www.European-agency.org/sites/default/files/Profile_for_Inclusive_Teacher_ProfessionalLearning.pdf

Brief project presentation KA2 (Strategic Partnership)

ALEXANDRU IOAN CUZA
UNIVERSITY of IAȘI

Universida_{de}Vigo

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Global Citizenship and Diversity Management Skills in Higher Education (GLOBDIVES, 2021-1-LT01-KA220-HED-000023530)

January 2022 – December 2023

Starting points:

Teaching of diversity management and global citizenship topics are at very different stages in partnering countries, fact determined by different levels of internalization.

E.g. Immigration has been more common in Finland first since the 1990s.

E.g. Diversity and inclusion are very current topics in Finland and Lithuania now due to work-based immigration.

E.g. Courses on intercultural competence are not compulsory at the University of Vigo or are taught to just some specializations in Social Sciences related courses at UAIC.

E.g. Global citizenship education is strongly rooted in educating how democracy works and how one can participate in democratic processes.

Project objectives

IO1: To create a pedagogical framework for teaching global citizenship and diversity management in higher education to students in Europe.

IO2: To create a 5 ECTS-course on Diversity Management and Global Citizenship.

IO3: To create a toolkit for teachers to integrate these topics into their courses no matter the curriculum (e.g. accounting to develop student's global mindset).

Note: Literature review and preliminary field research was conducted for each IO.

Learning activities:

- Intensive program for students in Lithuania (5 students/partner)
- Train the trainer – workshop for teachers in Spain (min. 5 teachers/partner)
- Local dissemination activities (100 teachers and future teachers/partner)

IO3 – Train the teacher toolkit (TTT)

The main goal of TTT is to represent a starting point for communication, debates and improved teaching methods among teachers willing to shift their pedagogical mindset and adopt more inclusive teaching lens/strategies.

Main objectives:

- raising awareness about diversity and inclusion in teaching practices
- offer guidelines for teaching in a diverse academic environment, for promoting diversity, equity and inclusion and creating a more inclusive learning environment.

IO3 – Train the teacher toolkit (TTT)

Main activities and results:

- *literature review* on diversity and inclusion competencies for HE teachers;
- *initial research on 149 teachers* in partner universities regarding the self-perceived level of diversity and inclusion competencies and their confidence in these competencies;
- gathering and/or creating *guidelines for higher education teachers* for creating a more inclusive learning environment;
- 30 *higher education* teachers from the 5 partner institutions participated in Train the Teachers Workshop (Ourense, Spain);
- 500 *higher education* teachers from the 5 partner institutions trained on managing diversity in classrooms (local workshops conducted by teachers who initially participated to the train the teachers' workshop).

Context for TTT development

Countries committed in 2015 to 'ensure inclusive and equitable quality education' by 2030, as stated in the fourth Sustainable Development Goal (SDG4).

Most of the research and recommendations were directed to pre-university levels of education. Too little was done for higher education in terms of developing diversity and inclusion competencies for teachers in order to value and celebrate diversity in the classroom, to help students acquire the diversity and inclusion competencies required in a more and more diverse workplace.

Source: UNESCO (2020) Inclusive teaching: preparing all teachers to teach all students, p. 1, <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000374447>.

Context for TTT development

All over the world, layers of discrimination on the basis of gender, remoteness, wealth, disability, ethnicity, language, migration, displacement, incarceration, sexual orientation, gender identity and expression, religion and other beliefs and attitudes deny students the right to be educated with their peers or to receive education of the same quality.

Microaggressions exist and can be prevented before entering the workplace environment if a proper education is offered to future employees. Working with diverse colleagues in a productive way, while each employee's wellbeing is reached needs to be exercised more and higher education environment can be such a place.

Context for TTT development

Cultural misunderstandings don't usually arise when everything is going well, but when we feel threatened or uncomfortable in a new environment, when we tend to go back "to the basics", to the values instilled in us when we were young.

Meeting with other cultures offer the opportunity to discover and understand our own culture better, by referring to another/other cultures, not better or less good, but just different.

However, not being prepared in this regard might cause anxiety and some reactions that can harm good relationships.

Context for TTT development

Most of the time we consider culture differences when referring to the national one, but in fact there are multiple other layers such as region, age, gender, profession, organizational culture or personality. All these cultural layers simultaneously and permanently influence the way students receive, interpret and use information, learn and behave later in professional life.

If we do not adapt our own teaching and assessment style to this very wide palette of cultural diversity in its broadest sense, we will not achieve the best learning outcomes, often wrongly attributing student failure to causes related to their behavior, even though the causes that are most often common could be also related to our behavior, which we do not discuss. This adaptation is necessary not only when we work with students from different national cultures, but also when we work - and this happens all the time - with students who are different from the perspective of other cultural layers.

1. Diversity and inclusion competencies for higher education teachers

1.1.

General aspects on higher education teachers' competencies

Higher education teachers' role

The research underlines the need for teachers to have high adaptability skills due to a high diversity of learning environments, different learning needs of students (Vogt and Rogalla, 2009).

Some research focused on higher education teachers' role: *a teacher as educator*, his/her professionalism having positive impact on students' learning outcomes (Mahulae et al., 2020), a model for students (Cebrián et al., 2020).

Thus, there is a growing body of literature that focuses on general frameworks of teachers' competencies.

Teaching competencies are defined as "an integrated set of personal characteristics, knowledge, skills and attitudes that are needed for effective performance in various teaching contexts" (Tigelaar et al., 2004).

Examples of higher education (HE) teachers' competencies framework

- There are different frameworks for HE teachers' competencies (developed for teachers, no matter the education level, others for HE teachers all over the world, while others were developed at country/ university level)
- Where could diversity and inclusion competencies be introduced?

Tigelaar et al., 2004 (Domains)	European Association for QA in HE, 2009 (Domains)	Duță, Pânișoară, Pânișoară (2014)
Person as Teacher	Personality competence	Scientific competence
The teacher as expert on content knowledge	Professionalism competence	Teaching competence
The teacher as facilitator of learning processes	Educational competence	Transversal competencies
The teacher as organiser	'Scientificity' competence	Relational competences
The teacher as scholar/lifelong learner	Communication competence	Vocation and dedication
	Digitality competence	Experience in educational institutions
		Self-assessment and Professional Development
		Research

1.2.

Literature review on diversity management and inclusion in teaching in partner countries

1.2.1. Literature review on diversity and inclusion teachers' competencies

- Competencies related to diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) are needed especially in teaching multicultural groups in international degree programs in higher education, however many other situations require teachers to manage diversity in class and to create an inclusive learning environment. (e.g. disability, age, professional background, educational background).
- No study was identified in defining diversity and inclusion competencies for higher education teachers, however multiple studies were conducted on teachers' multicultural competencies and some on inclusive competencies or diversity-oriented teacher. Some examples will be offered in the next pages.

Multicultural competencies for higher education teachers

Multicultural competencies could represent a first step for developing diversity-oriented teacher competencies frameworks.

Some examples of scales:

- Spanieman et al (2011) – Multicultural teaching competencies scale, 16 items, 2 factors, (1) multicultural teaching skills and (2) multicultural teaching knowledge
- Hsiao (2015) – Culturally Responsive Teacher Preparedness Scale, 18 items, 3 factors, (1) curriculum and instruction, (2) relationship and expectation establishment, and (3) group belonging formation.
- Erdem (2020) – Multicultural Competence Scale for Prospective Teachers: Development, Validation and Measurement Invariance, 14 items (1) awareness, (2) skills, (3) knowledge

Diversity-oriented teacher framework (all levels of teaching)

OECD recommendations in order to be a diversity-oriented teacher are
(Center for Educational Research and Innovation – Teacher Education for
Diversity)

- Critical self-evaluation of own teaching style
- Treating all students equally
- Inclusive teaching
- Knowing the students/learning about students
- Multiple instructional strategies

Source: adaptation from

<https://www.oecd.org/education/ceri/toolkitonteachingfordiversity-valuingandencouragingdiversityintheclassroom.htm>.

Teachers' competencies for inclusive education

Inclusive teaching requires teachers to recognize the experiences and abilities of every student, embrace the idea that each student's learning capacity is open ended, and be open to diversity.

Source: UNESCO (2020) Inclusive teaching: preparing all teachers to teach all students.
<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000374447>

Core values and competence areas of inclusive teaching

Core values	Competence areas	
Support all learners	Promote academic, practical, social and emotional learning for all	Engage effective teaching approaches in heterogenous classes based on understanding of a variety of learning processes and how to support them
Work with others	Work with parents and families to engage them effectively in learning	Work with other education professionals, including collaboration with other teachers
Value learner diversity	Understand inclusive education (e.g. it is based in belief in equality, human rights and democracy for all)	Respect, value and view learner diversity as an asset
Engage in professional development	Be reflective practitioners (i.e. systematically evaluate one's own performance)	View initial teacher education as the foundation for ongoing professional learning

Teacher profile for inclusive education (adapted for primary school teachers, starting from the core values areas of inclusive teaching, UNESCO)

Source:
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1307648.pdf>

Countries differ in how they define inclusion in education

- 10% of countries have general or inclusive education laws that address inclusion as a concept that refers to all learners
- 17% of countries have adopted an inclusive education policy that addresses inclusion as a concept that refers to all learners (two-thirds explicitly referred to teacher training)
- 75% of plans reviewed promote or envisage inclusion (49 explicitly indicate an aim to provide teacher training on inclusion, either general or directed at a target group)
- in some countries and territories, teacher competency standards focus on the inclusion of all learners and influence how teachers are trained.

Source: UNESCO (2020) Inclusive teaching: preparing all teachers to teach all students, p.3-5,
<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000374447>

Countries differ in how they define inclusion in education

- Preparing teachers for inclusion should not be treated as a specialized subject that focuses on teaching specific groups; rather, it should be mainstreamed.
- A teacher education system that accounts for diversity from the outset, instead of taking a piecemeal approach for certain groups, allows for a more effective use of resources (European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education, 2011).
- Such an approach also marks a shift away from categorizations, which often result in stigma, marginalization and exclusion.

Source: UNESCO (2020) Inclusive teaching: preparing all teachers to teach all students, p.6,
<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000374447>

The four models – development stages of the education

Exclusion stage – when students are denied access to the education

Segregation: groups of diverse students are educated separately

Integration: placing students with diverse needs in mainstream education settings with some adaptations and resources, but on condition that they can fit into pre-existing structures, attitudes and an unaltered environment (UNESCO, 2017).

Inclusion: a process that helps overcome barriers limiting the presence, participation and achievement of all learners. It is about changing the system to fit the student, not changing the student to fit the system.

The four models of education

Exclusion

Segregation

Integration

Inclusion

Source: Cerna et. al (2021), Promoting inclusive education for diverse societies: A conceptual framework, OECD Education Working Papers No. 260,

Self-reflection: How learning takes place in your university/ faculty/ classroom?

Even though the four models are considered usually at macro level, international/national policies, laws, it can easily be considered at micro-level.

Think of students' nationality, ethnic background, but also socioeconomic status, religion, educational background, professional experience, gender identity and sexual orientation, age, disability, giftedness. How diverse are students from your classroom in terms of the layers above?

What is the model of education (previous slide) that represents best the students in your classroom, in this context?

How are students interacting, working in teams during class or outside class?

- Are people with low income kept apart from a team?
- Do students with a different nationality than the majority exclude themselves, do they create teams on their own?

What can you do in order to create a more inclusive learning environment?

Teachers training needs on inclusion topics

The learning environment in the classroom becomes more and more diverse.

Teachers might feel overwhelmed, but with proper training they can be again in command.

Teachers need more opportunities for professional development on inclusion

Percentage of teachers reporting a high need for training in two inclusion-related areas, selected middle- and high-income countries, 2018

Note: Education systems selected are those in which teachers reported a higher-than-average need for professional development on teaching students with special needs, i.e. students for whom a special learning need has been formally identified because of mental, physical or emotional disadvantage. Source: OECD (2019b).

Source: UNESCO (2020) Inclusive teaching: preparing all teachers to teach all students, p.3, <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000374447>

Source: https://www.european-agency.org/sites/default/files/Profile_for_Inclusive_Teacher_ProfessionalLearning.pdf

TPL policy needs in the ecosystem of inclusive education systems

Teacher training on inclusion in higher education

- Most references are about how teachers are trained in their higher education studies to work in an inclusive manner, not about how they apply inclusiveness in higher education
- A review for the 2020 Global Education Monitoring Report of teacher education for inclusion in Argentina, Ethiopia, Ghana, the Lao People's Democratic Republic and Zanzibar (United Republic of Tanzania) found policies on training for inclusion in all the countries at the primary education level and a clear trend of extending teacher development for inclusion to early childhood care and education, secondary education and higher and adult education.
- However, most efforts focused on students with disabilities, though there were some efforts towards a whole-school approach and system transformation to build inclusive school communities and cultures (Lehtomäki et al., 2020).

Source: UNESCO (2020) Inclusive teaching: preparing all teachers to teach all students, <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000374447>.

Challenges for the future

- While laws, plans, strategies and policies are increasingly issued all over the world in the name of inclusive education to fulfil the commitments countries made in the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and the fourth Sustainable Development Goal, two challenges are commonly encountered:
- First, many teacher education programmes are yet to embrace this broad concept of inclusion, instead treating inclusion in teacher education first and foremost as a special topic, imparting special skills, to be deployed in special settings.
- Second, even when countries strike the right tone, there is often a distance between declarations and actions, especially with respect to preparing teachers.

1.2.2. Literature review within the project partners countries

	University Teachers' Knowledge on D&I	University Teachers' Skills on D&I	University Teachers' Feelings (including confidence level) about D&I	University Teachers' Values related to D&I	Train the teachers on D&I issues	Level of teachers' awareness on D&I
Finland	H	H	M	M	H	M
Germany	M	M	L	Not available	H	M
Lithuania	L	L	L	M	L	L
Romania	L	L	L	M	L	L
Spain	M	M	L	M	L	M

Legend: L-low, M-medium, H-high

Source: Literature review of partner universities

Finland – Initiatives

- Initiative of the Ministry of Education (2007) Educating for Global Responsibility
- Cultural Awareness (3 ECTS) is a compulsory course in teachers' pedagogical studies
- Finnish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment: Project (2021-2023): D&I into Finnish Work life.
- Curriculum guidelines for secondary education

Finland – Main findings

- D&I is included in compulsory pedagogical studies (60 ECTS) for teachers teaching in universities of applied sciences, but not required from teachers and professors at scientific universities
- Courses such as Inclusion and Diversity, Inclusion and Global Education for example can be found from compulsory pedagogical studies and in Master programmes for pedagogics
- Generally good awareness on D&I, but if the teacher does not teach students in international degree programmes, awareness can be more limited. Good general English language skills help.
- Challenges of teaching multicultural groups – First Aid Kit for LAB and LUT staff (Jaana Häkli, Feb 2023) and Cultural knowledge training on countries such as Nepal, Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka (Derek Mitchell)
- New cultures (Africa, Southern Asia, the Middle East) and accessibility features e.g. to students with disabilities are still points of training sessions for teachers.

Finland – Sources

- Henriksson, H. (2022):
https://www.doria.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/185863/henriksson_heidi.pdf?sequence=1
- Ministry of Education (2007): Educating for Global Responsibility.
<https://julkaisut.valtioneuvosto.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/79403/opm31.pdf>
- Cultural Awareness 3 ECTS as a compulsory course in teachers' pedagogical studies
<https://hamk.opinto-opas.fi/curricula/degreeprogrammes/groups/plan?groupId=82950&planId=82900>
- Curriculum guidelines for secondary education:
https://www.oph.fi/sites/default/files/documents/lukion-opetussuunnitelman-perusteet-pahkinankuoressa-saavutettava_0.pdf
- Journals:
- <https://journal.fi/aikuiskasvatus>
- <https://ktl.jyu.fi/fi/julkaisut/kasvatus>
- <https://lehti.yliopistopedagogiikka.fi/>

Germany – Initiatives

- Project: Transnational learning for Europe in border regions (University of Trier) - <https://www.edu-gr.eu/>. Scope: development of educational resources for teacher training/continuing education to include European topics and cross-border thinking into teaching practice.
- List of tools and examples to use in the university classroom: <https://sqb-hetkom.de/format/konzeptbausteine/>

Germany – Main findings

- Teaching and teacher education research can now draw on extensive empirical studies in the context of "dealing with heterogeneity", but there is still a clear deficit in this area for higher education.
- "Diversity Competence" consists of 5 factors: adapting teaching-learning-processes to a diverse group; using suitable didactics/methods; acting adequate in social interactions; appreciative attitude; references to the higher educational system
- Topics identified in university initiatives for developing KSA for teachers on D&I: how to diagnose heterogeneity/diversity in the classroom? How to integrate different styles of learning and expressing knowledge? How to adapt to and influence diverse group dynamics in the classroom? Being aware of students' individuality, perspectives and differences.

Germany – Sources

- Peer reviewed journals, working paper series, conference proceedings: <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-658-09477-5>
- Books and teaching notes: <https://www.utb.de/doi/book/10.36198/9783838556031>
- University initiatives, for developing KSA for teachers on diversity and inclusion topic: <https://www.edu-gr.eu/>, <https://sqb-hetkom.de/toolbox/>

Lithuania – Initiatives

- Respect and Support (a series of videos and articles on different people at our Institution and their struggles or point of view. It's aimed at better understanding the community about D&I, not the teaching content or values) - <https://www.kaunokolegija.lt/?s=gerbiam+ir+palaikom&search-type=site-search>
- Equal Possibilities Policy: https://www.kaunokolegija.lt/kk_wp_content/uploads/2022/04/KK_Lygiu-galimybiu-politika.pdf
- Equality and Diversity at HEIs: https://www.lygybe.lt/data/public/uploads/2015/11/visas-leidiny-su-virseliu_aukstosios-mokyklos.pdf
- Lithuanian Ministry of Education – Inclusive Teaching: <https://www.nsa.smm.lt/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Svietimas-Lietuvoje-2022-web.pdf>
- National Education Agency – Towards Inclusion: <https://www.nsa.smm.lt/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/Itraukties-link.-Ka-turi-zinoti-mokykla.Atmintine-mokykloms.pdf>

Lithuania – Main findings

- There are some concerns at governmental level for preparing teachers for diversity and inclusion in teaching
- Authorities, organizations and teachers are aware that they need more training on D&I
- Teachers are not ready to work with disabled students – teaching means and methods are not adapted to their needs; the physical environment of HEIs is not adapted to their needs
- There is no systematic approach to inclusion of the disabled in HEIs
- Lithuanian teachers think their readiness to work with different students in terms of cultural background and different language is one of the weakest. 1/3 of teachers say they are stressed when they have to prepare and give lessons to students with special learning needs

Lithuania – Sources

- Šileikytė, D. (2019). Are HEIs ready to accept (teach) disabled students?
<https://www.svietimonaujienos.lt/ar-aukstosios-mokyklos-pasiruosusios-priimti-negalia-turincius-studentus/>
- National website, aligned with EU provisions:
<https://education.ec.europa.eu/lt/focus-topics/improving-quality/inclusive-education/migrants-and-refugees>

Romania – Initiatives

- Initiatives identified stem mostly from the academic teachers' needs, who admit that they need to be trained better on D&I
- All teachers at all levels are trained for the basics in pedagogy, which covers inclusion of all children in classes
- Two universities signed The Diversity Charter
- A federation created in 2015 by NGOs in education initiated different projects in order to raise awareness of governmental institutions regarding the impact that the education laws could have, the importance of teachers' development, emphasizing also on developing inclusive competencies for teachers.

Romania – Main findings

- The topics of diversity and inclusion are not covered enough in teacher education in general and in academic teachers' education in particular
- Some initiatives have been identified, still there is no clear concern for the topic from a governmental point of view.
- Each university trains future higher education teachers in pedagogy, but diversity and inclusion topic might be integrated within different topics, no specific course in this regard being identified within curricula.
- Teachers feel the need to be better trained for diversity and inclusion, even though the topic is not very clear to them.

Romania – Sources

- Psycho-pedagogical module on initial formation of teachers for inclusion of all children (2017),
https://revcurentjur.ro/old/arhiva/attachments_202104/recjurid214_9F.pdf
- In 2022 the University of Bucharest signed The Diversity Charter –
<https://unibuc.ro/the-university-of-bucharest-signatory-of-the-diversity-charter/?lang=en>
- NGO debates (2017) Identifying the competency profile of the teacher,
<http://coalitiaedu.ro/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/Document-Pozitie-Profilul-de-competente-al-profesorului.pdf>

Spain – Initiatives

- Initiatives are mainly identified in the literature (peer reviewed journals, working paper series, conference proceedings, books, teaching notes, conferences) that are meant to raise awareness about the issues.
- One university initiative for intercultural mediation and communication was identified.
- One KSA guide for university teachers on diversity was identified.
- No governmental initiative was identified at national level.

Spain – Main findings

- There is a significant number of articles identifying the need to better train teachers in Spain on D&I and teaching in diverse classes.
- The intercultural model is considered the most adequate to manage diversity and train critical citizenship. Therefore, the need to determine what are active methodologies (cooperative and collaborative), and their function within the framework of teacher training for interculturality needs to be defined.
- Intercultural aspects are considered quite often for language classes, not so much for other classes
- Teachers consider themselves to be interculturally competent and think they use techniques to implement intercultural education, but they do not show either sufficient attitudes, or use techniques to develop students' intercultural skills.
- Suggestions: introduce contents on intercultural scope in teachers' initial and continuous training, create strategic bonds between universities and the educational administration, keeping in mind the development of intercultural competences from within the educational system.

Spain – Sources

- https://www.comillas.edu/Documentos/CELEBRANDO_LA_DIVERSIDAD_MARTA_SANDOVAL.pdf
- https://formacionpermanente.uned.es/tp_actividad/actividad/mediacion-intercultural-en-contextos-socioeducativos
- Livro de atas do II Congresso Internacional de Mediação Social: a Europa como espaço de diálogo intercultural e de mediação (core.ac.uk)
- Convivencia y Educación Intercultural: análisis y propuestas pedagógicas. – Juan José Leiva Olivencia – Google Libros

Conclusions on literature reviews from partner countries

- There are differences at country level in terms of knowledge about diversity and inclusion.
- Most countries have not yet created a clear plan for truly implementing diversity and inclusion practices in HEIs.
- Some teachers consider themselves prepared for diversity and inclusion, but do not have the KSA they would need or like to have.
- If teachers are trained, most are trained on general principles for teaching students, not referring specifically to academic students.
- If they don't deliver classes in international languages, teachers perceive to have more barriers in teaching diverse groups.
- Curricula are not adapted to students with special needs, therefore teachers do not feel prepared to deliver courses to these students.

1.3.

Research on diversity management and inclusion competencies in partner universities

Survey on teachers from the 5 partner universities (March- April 2023)

AIMS:

- **identify the importance of different diversity and inclusion topics to be addressed into curriculum;**
- **analyse self-perceived level of diversity and inclusion competencies**

Sample description:

- 149 respondents
- 65.8% are between 35-55 years old,
- 54.36% have between 11-25 years of teaching experience
- 66.4% are female
- 75.17% teach courses in business administration or social sciences fields
- 79.2% teach international students at least 1 time a year in the home countries or abroad
- 71.1% teach abroad
- 51% participated to trainings related to diversity management

Importance of diversity topics to be included in courses

(differences of profession, cultural awareness, gender, preventing extremism, people with disability, religion orientation, ageism, LGBTIQ)

1. The first three **most important and addressed diversity topics** are: *professional differences, cultural awareness* and *gender equality*, while the least addressed ones are *ageism* and *LGBTIQ rights*.

2. **Significant differences addressing the diversity topics were registered** considering the ***university, faculty, gender*** variables:

A. UAIC considers cultural awareness, religion orientation and profession differences as being more important topics, compared to the other 4 partners.

B. Preventing racism topic is considered more important by teachers from Health and Welfare faculties, and least important by teachers in Engineering field; while religion and LGBTIQ topics are considered more important by teachers from Education and Social Sciences field

Importance of diversity topics to be included in the course (cont.)

3. **Significant differences addressing the diversity topics** were registered considering also the *teaching international students* and *diversity related training participation* variables:

A. cultural awareness is considered more important by teachers who teach international students on weekly or monthly basis compared to those with no teaching experience or those who teach 1-3 times a year during short-term mobilities.

B. religion orientation and LGBTIQ rights topics are considered more important by people who attended a diversity training compared to those who did not.

Self-perceived level of diversity and inclusion competencies

- Overall, respondent teachers had better perceptions on their *establishing strong, supportive relationships with students' skills, developing students' critical thinking* and consider themselves as being *aware of the necessity to critically examine them own beliefs* about diverse students and of the necessity to *opt for continuous training*.
- Respondents declared that they are missing the knowledge to *apply different techniques and strategies to evaluate diverse students, to integrate topics and events specific to diverse (minorities) groups* into their courses, the knowledge of *particular teaching strategies that promote diversity and inclusion*.
- Teachers who attended diversity and inclusion trainings perceived themselves more confident in their diversity and inclusion competencies.

Self-perceived level of diversity and inclusion competencies

- The diversity and inclusion competencies were considered to have 3 components (resulted from the Factor analyses): (1) integrating diversity in teaching (9 items), (2) self-reflection and development (4 items), (3) development of students' transferable skills (3 items). The lowest level of competence was registered for integrating diversity in teaching component.
- **The level of confidence in diversity and inclusion competencies varies** considering *university, frequencies of teaching international students, diverse training attendance variables*, but not considering the *teaching abroad* variable. This could mean that the length of interaction with international or diverse students in general needs to be longer in order to have the chance to enrich the diversity and inclusion competencies.
- *Teachers from Social Sciences faculties* perceived themselves as being *more knowledgeable* in integrating diversity in teaching compared to those in *Engineering* field.

Main conclusions of the research

- Addressing diversity and inclusion topics is very important no matter the course taught, no matter the faculty field.
- People with high level of confidence in their DI knowledge and creating inclusive environment skills also perceived having higher level of DI competences, thus training opportunities should be provided in a systematic way, at HEI level.
- Teaching mobility could be a driver to diversity and inclusion competencies development, however longer periods of interaction with diverse students or higher frequency of these mobilities should be considered.

2. Introducing diversity and inclusion into curriculum

2.1.

Importance of addressing diversity and inclusion topics

Main benefits (1)

- Managing diversity in education settles the ground for cross-cultural skills development required in the future work environment. Universities could offer the proper environment in which students can experience working with diverse colleagues.
- Diversity intelligence is a form of cultural intelligence and enhances learning opportunities, improves communication, teamwork, conflict management. Different opinions coming from different educational/intercultural background bring new lights into a classroom, make students think harder and provide clearer evidence for their opinions, while creating flexible mindsets.

Main benefits (2)

- Students develop social and emotional skills, including empathy, in proper diversity educational environments (psychologically safe, supportive atmosphere)
- Diversity in teaching offers all students the possibility to shine in the classroom, to feel they belong to the learning community, to improve self-efficacy as learners, to develop positive attitude towards the world.
- Diversity intelligence stimulates innovation, creativity and entrepreneurial thinking.

2.2.

General pedagogical recommendations

(developed based on OECD perspective)

Treating all students equally

A few ideas to start with:

- encourage all to talk in class, during debates, discussions
- find out in each stage of the course/homework/application if students encountered difficulties
- there are no 'good' or 'bad' students; there could be students interested in the topic/course or not; motivated to learn in that particular moment or not; for some students it is easier to connect the new information and skill to their background, for others it is more challenging; don't judge before you understand the situation each student is dealing with.

Knowing the students

A few ideas to start from:

- learn different things about students such as learning styles, preferred materials to be studied, their background – previous education, socioeconomic status, social environment; this will help you better understand the reactions they have; when necessary, refer them to different services.
- you can always use different self-assessment tests or games in order to know more about students and help students better know each other, especially if teamwork activities exist.
- calibrate time spent for explaining the requirements; in some cases, there might be the need to offer individual tutorship.

Multiple instructional strategies (I)

A few ideas to start with:

- Ask yourself: What is the background of the authors used in class references? (gender, age, nationality, socioeconomic status, etc.) Presenting multiple perspectives will make students encounter diversity one more time.
- Make sure you have different types of sources for documentation: reading, listening, video. Kids in kindergarten draw, write, sing, dance, listen to stories, create art; what activities could be transferred to your adult students? Could they create maps, use software, make essays, solve case studies in teams and/or individual, listen to a biography of the authors studied, talk to their future clients (customers, employees, patients, students, parents, etc.)?

Multiple instructional strategies (II)

A few ideas to start with:

- Do they have the possibility to choose from 'different packages' of tasks in order to be evaluated?
- Make sure you are not assessing only their knowledge or skills directly related to the course topic, but also their inclusive behaviour, the cross-cultural skills, or empathy proven. Self-reflection on how the homework was done, how a specific topic links to their background, how a specific topic will help them in the future professional life could be also an idea.

2.3.

How to integrate diversity topic in Social Sciences and Business Administration fields – some examples

Example 1: Where are the 'CULTUREMES'?

Aim(s): Detect 'culturemes' and examine their (varied) interpretation according to each participant's background and experience.

Estimated time: Total: 40–50 minutes; **divided as follows:**

10–15 minutes to watch some scenes/official trailers from the three movies.

15 minutes for discussion among each group.

15–20 minutes to compare points of view among the groups.

Description of the activity:

Organize participants in MULTICULTURAL groups of 5. Each group will choose 2 persons: 1 to write down what would be said during their discussion and another to be their spokesperson.

Play some scenes/official trailers from the movies *My Big Fat Greek Wedding 1, 2 and 3*.

After watching the scenes/official trailers, groups will be asked to highlight possible 'culturemes' in the three movies. After that, they will be requested to discuss them based on their cultural backgrounds and previous experiences.

The spokesperson of each group will be asked to share with the other groups what his/her group had discussed earlier. After that, a debate among all groups will be held to discuss different opinions and perceptions.

Materials and resources:

A wide room where groups can be divided comfortably.

A television/computer, projector, loudspeakers and internet connection.

Observations:

Instead of movies, this activity could be developed using TV series from different countries/cultures.

Example 2: Weird Publicity ... Or Just Different?!

Aim(s):

Recognize how promoting the same product in different countries/cultures can vary (considerably) depending on the country/culture it is advertised within.

Estimated time: 50-55 minutes, divided as follows:

10-15 minutes to search the internet for the required advertisements.

20 minutes for analysis and discussion among each group.

20 minutes to compare points of view among the groups.

Description of the activity:

Organize participants in MULTICULTURAL groups of 5. Each group will choose 2 persons: 1 to write down what would be said during their discussion and another to be their spokesperson.

Ask each group to search on the internet for several advertisements of the same product from different countries (for example, Coca Cola, Perfumes, Tuna cans, sportswear, etc.) (10-15 min).

After watching the advertisements, each group will be asked to highlight potential cultural aspects and analyse them according to their corresponding cultures/societies (20 min).

The spokesperson of each group will be asked to share with the other groups what his/her group had discussed earlier. After that, a debate among all groups will be held to discuss different opinions and perceptions.

Materials and resources:

A wide room where groups can be divided comfortably.

Computer(s), projector, loudspeakers and internet connection.

Example 3: What does your garden say about you?

Aim: Discover how plants and gardens are a true reflection of the culture they are found within.

Estimated time: 45–55 minutes, divided as follows:

5 minutes for groups to choose the images they will use during the activity.

20–25 minutes for discussion among each group.

20–25 minutes to compare points of view among the groups.

Description of the activity:

Organize participants in MONOCULTURAL groups of 5. Each group will choose 2 persons: 1 to write down what would be said during their discussion and another to be their spokesperson.

The moderator will display on the screen images of some plants/trees/natural landscapes.

Each group will choose an image from those displayed on the screen.

After that, each group will develop a discussion regarding that image and how it reveals/relates to its corresponding potential culture. In this aspect, groups will bear in mind, also, different climates in the corresponding regions where those plants/trees/natural landscapes are found and how they affect people's character, clothes, gastronomy, water resources, etc.

The spokesperson of each group will be asked to share with the other groups what his/her group had discussed earlier regarding the image they have chosen. After that, a debate among all groups will be held to discuss different opinions and perceptions.

Materials and resources:

A wide room where groups can be divided comfortably.

Computer(s), projector and internet connection.

Observations:

Instead of virtual images, this activity can be developed using hard copies distributed among participants.. 70

2.4.

Raising awareness on diversity and inclusion importance in STEM

Researchers have found evidence that beliefs about the nature of knowledge predict pedagogical practices; because STEM sciences are more “positivist” and “quantitativist” comparing to the “intepretivist-constructivist” and “qualitativist” SSHA, their pedagogical practices will be adapted accordingly and might make students with a previous non-quantitative background feel less capable or less fitted (impostor syndrome). Researchers even talk about a „STEM ways of thinking (SWoT)“, that might hurt interdisciplinary teaching and learning (Slavit et al, 2019)

STEM higher education fields have also large numbers of international students, and thus multicultural environments in class. Due to the quantitative, technical nature of STEM fields, teachers are not always aware of, or possess the appropriate knowledge to deal with students’ ethnic misbehaviours. As a consequence, their approach to diversity in the classroom might contribute to an unfavorable educational position for ethnic minority students, stronger or weaker depending on the cultural intelligence or societal readiness to discuss multicultural education issues.

There is a large debate about values-based or values-neutral education. Culturally relevant pedagogy supports students in ways that leverage students' own cultures through three tenets: academic success, cultural competence, and sociopolitical consciousness. If STEM practitioners believe that their disciplines are culture-free or cultural values-free, they may not enact culturally relevant pedagogy in their courses. (Shultz et al., 2022).

Shultz et al. (2022) research revealed that though never asked directly, some instructors made statements reflecting a "culture-free" belief about knowledge in their discipline such as "To me, mathematics has no color". However, they reported that they approached different pedagogical styles when needed (e.g. because of interpersonal obligation). The authors concluded that: "Instructors' ability to express two contradictory views may indicate that professional development does not have to change an instructor's epistemological beliefs about their discipline (...)."

The changes proposed should enable instructors to decide to cultivate students' cultural competence and sociopolitical consciousness.

STEM fields should address potential diversity issues even within their own nationality students. With more people moving abroad for education and work, many countries are becoming multicultural in population, and many countries experience a returning home for former migrant families. Hence, developing multicultural attitudes is becoming imperative to prevent negative thoughts and feelings toward minorities that may translate into discriminatory behaviors toward them, and at the same time to prevent inappropriate teaching for reverse-aculturated students (those who have to adapt back to the cultural norms of the origin country, or organizational norms of the home country university, after they were abroad).

One way to ensure this is through multicultural education. The aim of multicultural education is to ensure that students from diverse racial, ethnic, and social-class groups will experience educational equality.

3. Managing a diverse classroom in higher education

Introduction

Managing a diverse classroom starts with being aware of the diversity among students. Diversity exists on different layers, starting from personality and other individual differences like nationality, ethnicity, age, disability, to external and organizational one - organizational culture or professional background.

Considering the national culture level, we are dealing with intercultural diversity as more and more international teaching environments occur.

After presenting some instruments for teachers' self-assessment, a short presentation on cultural aspects to be considered will be made. Strategies regarding intercultural diversity management in classroom and scenarios and possible solutions will be also presented.

Some scenarios will refer to cultural differences while others will deal with gender, socioeconomic status, educational and professional background or level of anxiety control. Although some of the scenarios refer to specific countries, we don't intend to contribute to stereotypes - similar scenarios can happen in any country depending on other differences (e.g. socioeconomic, age, gender).

Preamble (I)

Cultural identities of our students matter

“Even though some of us might wish to conceptualize our classrooms as culturally neutral or might choose to ignore the cultural dimensions, students cannot check their sociocultural identities at the door, nor can they instantly transcend their current level of development..

Therefore, it is important that the pedagogical strategies we employ in the classroom reflect an understanding of social identity development so that we can anticipate the tensions that might occur in the classroom and be proactive about them”

(Ambrose, Bridges, DiPietro & Lovett, 2010)

Preamble (II) – Issues in the class

- Different levels of prior knowledge, due to backgrounds in high school or bachelor or master level
- Different motivations (personality + career)
- Different current level of development (emotional, cognitive)
- Economically/socially disadvantaged groups, rural-urban
- Group/team work with different nationalities
- Neurodiversity
- High achieving students feeling overlooked
- Teachers are influenced by all 7 cultural layers and own biases matter

All these affect learning, class participation, assessment equity, retention and completion rates, future behavior in society.

3.1.

Higher education teachers' awareness on diverse classroom

A. Critical self –evaluation of own believes and diversity and inclusion related skills

- Be aware of potential unconscious bias. Self-reflection on subjective discrimination or test might help in this regard: <https://implicit.harvard.edu/implicit/education.html>
- COF assessment – intercultural skills
- Inclusive Classroom Self-Assessment for Educators
(https://www.turnerconsultinggroup.ca/uploads/2/9/5/6/29562979/inclusive_classroom_self-assessment__1_.pdf)
- self-reflection tool for (psychology) teachers:
<https://www.apa.org/ed/precollege/topss/considering-diversity/diversity-reflection-tool.pdf>

B. Inclusive teaching competencies means (European Agency for Development in Special Needs, 2012)

- **Valuing Learner Diversity** – learner difference is considered as a resource and an asset to education. The areas of competence within this core value relate to: conceptions of inclusive education; the teacher’s view of learner difference.

Supporting All Learners – teachers have high expectations for all learners’ achievements. The areas of competence within this core value relate to: promoting the academic, practical, social and emotional learning of all learners; effective teaching approaches in heterogeneous classes.

Working With Others – collaboration and teamwork are essential approaches for all teachers. The areas of competence within this core value relate to: working with student peers; working with a range of other educational professionals.

Personal Professional Development – teaching is a learning activity and teachers take responsibility for their lifelong learning. The areas of competence within this core value relate to: teachers as reflective practitioners; initial teacher education as a foundation for ongoing professional learning and development.

C. Cultural adaptation and adjustment

•It's important to understand what are the typical features of a cultural adaptation and adjustment process international students go through when they move to a completely new cultural environment to study. They often go through phases such as *Honeymoon*, *Culture Shock*, *Adaptation* and *Re-Entry Shock* as part of the adaptation / integration process. The entire time is filled with cultural learning and unlearning practices they had in their home country. Cultural adaptation takes time and its length varies from one person to another.

•It's important to recognize severe symptoms of culture shock as these can require medical care. Symptoms are e.g. insomnia, sleepiness, mental and physical isolation from others, depression and sadness, losing or gaining weight as people react differently to distress. Some people eat comfort food and gain weight or can have suddenly a lot of pimples on their face, other people can lose their appetite because of distress. Do not also forget that young students can have very weak skills in cooking because it could be so that their mothers have prepared the meals for them all their lives as this is typical especially in collectivist cultures.

Stages of Cultural Adaptation

Lähde
Rajasekar, J. 2013

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/272723599_Culture_Shock_in_a_Global_World_Factors_Affecting_Culture_Shock_Experienced_by_Expatriates_in_Oman_and_Omani_Expatriates_Abroad

Geert Hofstede's 6 Cultural Dimensions Theory

The theory of the 6 cultural dimensions helps in understanding especially differences in values, behavior patterns, preferences in study methods, teaching methods that you will face in teaching multicultural student groups.

More specifically if you start to get students from completely new cultures, using Hofstede's country comparison tool can help you familiarize with new cultures. In this tool 102 countries are listed and the latest figures are from 2022, the oldest might date back to the 1970s as the first version of the research was conducted then.

Find the country comparison tool here: <https://www.hofstede-insights.com/country-comparison-tool>

What are these dimensions about in a nutshell?

Power distance: understanding of hierarchy and authority, emotional distance between a superior and a subordinate or a teacher and a student.

Individualism vs. collectivism: the sense of identity and belonging

Motivation towards Achievement and Success: the importance of wealth and status, gender roles incl. woman's position in society

Uncertainty avoidance: the ability to tolerate not knowing what is going to happen e.g. in the near future

Long-term orientation: understanding about time and patience; planning of the future

Indulgence: the importance of free time and having fun in one's life

POWER DISTANCE

HIGH POWER DISTANCE

- Students respect the teacher and acknowledge his/her authority.
- Teacher teaches vs. self-direction and problem-based learning (Who does the work? Who is lazy?)
- Teacher is a guru. Does not question knowledge or competences of less interaction in class.
- Student might avoid teacher's eye contact.
- Who has done the decision about the degree programme in the admission phase? What is the motivation to study?
- Problems or misunderstandings are not brought up.
- Self-reflection skills are non-existing and have not been learned before. Unrealistic understanding of one's skills and future prospects.

LOW POWER DISTANCE

- Students are encouraged to self-reflection, innovative thinking, searching for opportunities and making choices for themselves.
- Self-reflection has started in kindergarten.
- Teachers and students meet each other as equals and teachers consider themselves to be guides in students' learning path.
- Students ask for clarifications and express their opinions.

INDIVIDUALISM VS. COLLECTIVISM

HIGH INDIVIDUALISM

- “Me, me, me -thinking” rules
- Own opinions matter
- Students complete studies for themselves and are responsible for their learning outcomes
personal motivation, personal rewards
- Personal study paths and flexibility in curricula
- Recognition of prior learning based on work experience or studies elsewhere →flexibility and individual study plans
- Self-direction is familiar since secondary education
- Use electives / complementary studies to meet their personal interests
- Making mistakes: loss of self-respect, problems with motivation

LOW INDIVIDUALISM / HIGH COLLECTIVISM

- “We, we, we -thinking”, solving problems together
- Begging for help and want individual guidance
- Own opinions have not been asked before
self-reflection takes time and practice
- Power of one’s family and community,
ganging up with fellow country men
- Students learn in teams, helping a friend in tasks/exams (cheating), rewarding a team/
community
- Rivalry between team members and multicultural teams
- Cheating and plagiarism = helping a friend
- Making mistakes: personal shame and loss of face in one’s community

MOTIVATION TOWARDS ACHIEVEMENT AND SUCCESS (dimension renamed in 2023)

HIGH MOTIVATION

- Students are ambitious and need to succeed.
- Students are used to rivalry keeping information / knowledge to themselves
- Students live to study
- Authoritarian teachers
- Symbols of wealth are visible
- Knowledge and authority of a female teacher/professor might be questioned in degree programmes dominated by male students.
- Big dreams to succeed

LOW MOTIVATION

- Students value a good quality in life incl. free-time, parties and want to help each other out.
- Equity and fairness in studying, consensus in decision making.
- Principles of soft skills are highlighted.
- Life exists besides studies and study motivation can vary and other issues might take a lot of time.
- Gender equality is important.
- Modesty, humbleness, difficulties in receiving appraisal and low confidence in one's competences.

UNCERTAINTY AVOIDANCE

HIGH UNCERTAINTY AVOIDANCE

- Students want to avoid uncertainty and unawareness and want to avoid mistakes.
- Inner need to be hard-working and efficient, critical towards lower grades and aim at perfection
- What is the right answer in an essay?
- Good at memorizing, weaker at expressing own opinions or changing a point of view
- Might experience stress because aiming at perfectionism. Is there any life besides studies?
- Timing of studies vs. student exchange, scholarships etc. is important
- Need for clear instructions

LOW UNCERTAINTY AVOIDANCE

- Students are willing to take risks and are open to new ideas and experiments in teaching/learning
- Students enjoy their free-time →Are they lazy? They can easily get time management problems.
- Students learn in interactive teaching through dialogue and challenging the teacher.
- Less stress in life, satisfaction with lower grades
- Self-reflection skills have been practiced before

LONG-TERM ORIENTATION

HIGH LONG-TERM ORIENTATION

- Students accept changes easily. You can affect your own future with personal choices. Open to new learning experiments and intensive courses and popularity of online learning.
- Long-term plan for studies
- Scholarship principles affect studies and graduation.
- Working parallel to studies, voluntary work, non-paid internships
- Concept of truth/right and wrong varies depending on the situation and the position of the instructor.

LOW LONG-TERM ORIENTATION

- Students want continuity and to know their future plans and timetables early.
- Short-term goals in studies: one course at a time and is the student going to graduate within the regular study time?
- Fast results and answers are expected.
- Taking a gap year in studies.
- Truth is black and white. Fairness to everyone. Show your evaluation criteria!

INDULGENCE VS. RESTRAINT

INDULGENCE

- Large group of study partners
- Positive understanding of one's abilities and eager to grasp possibilities
- Good quality of life is based on a balance in studies and free-time.

RESTRAINT

- Free-time is not important.
- Feelings of stress
- Religion-based restrictions in one's life
- Isolation in student community due to parties' drinking nature

Lewis theory of communication profiles

a tool to understand communication differences among international students.

MULTI-ACTIVE COMMUNICATION STYLE

- Talkers of the world: talk most of the time and can talk for hours. Hence, can be seen as inefficient.
- Character features: extrovert, talkative, impatient, emotional.
- Body language is rich.
- Networking with people is important as students try to form networks with people as they never know whose help and expertise you might need one day.
- Seek for favours from those networks/friends; e.g. in studies, exams etc.
- Negotiate with confrontation and arguments.

MULTI-ACTIVE COMMUNICATION STYLE

- Interrupt easily as interruption is seen as a compliment. By interrupting you are truly listening to the speaker.
- Poor or unpredictable time management.
- Do several things at once, multi-tasking.
- Feelings come before task and students might have ready-made excuses for different kinds of situations.

- E.g. Latin American, Mediterranean, African cultures

REACTIVE COMMUNICATION STYLE

- Listeners of the world: listen most of the time. Answer questions as students when they are specifically asked to.
- Character features: introvert, patient, silent, respectful.
- Modest body language. Smile has many meanings.
- Long tolerance for silence.
- Don't like interruptions but serial conversations.
- Work in teams → Management of groups.
- Indirect communication because they don't say no but use euphemisms like *Maybe, We'll see, Let me think about it*, etc. instead.

REACTIVE COMMUNICATION STYLE

- Good time management skills but work flexible hours.
- Get the whole picture often and easily.
- Decisions are based on knowledge, expertise and personal user experiences for example. Students easily ask the teacher to decide upon their choices regarding studies (e.g. student exchange, thesis topic, internship etc.).
- Use both first-hand and researched information for the decision making.
- Seniority is highly respected and therefore students coming e.g. from Asia rarely argue with a teacher who is seen as a highly respected person.
- The concept of *must not lose face* is a central element of the culture.
- E.g. Asian cultures

LINEAR-ACTIVE COMMUNICATION STYLE

- Planners of the world: Balance between talking and listening, but planning is a central feature of the communication.
- Character features: introvert, patient, quiet, like privacy
- Limited body language but variations between nationalities.
- Strict time management and work according to fixed hours and timetables. (separation of work and private life, focus on the task and studies)
- Plan studies and assignments methodologically and do one thing at a time.

Frequent barriers to inclusivity efforts

- Insufficient resources
- Lack of time due to class sizes
- Denial of inequality
- Lack of awareness/lack of training (driver's metaphor)
- Teachers' fatigue
- Societal/institutional norms – “old attitudes die hard”
- Non-balanced approach to priorities
- Lack of engagement and leadership across HEIs

Supplementary reflections I

Mintz, 2023: “Two facets of diversity are typically treated in isolation: **identity diversity**—race, ethnicity, class, gender and sexual orientation—and **viewpoint diversity**—ideological, moral, religious and political. Even though the faculty is much more diverse than it was a generation ago, the professoriate’s characteristics “tend to evolve much more slowly than the general population.” Delayed retirement, stagnating (or in some instances, shrinking) faculty size and shifts in hiring toward fields with fewer diverse Ph.D.s mean that parity within the next thirty years is unlikely to be achieved without “dramatic changes in hiring, promotion and retention.”

Kite and Clark, 2022: “An important goal in diversity education is helping students recognize their biases. Whether they are implicit or explicit, **biases stem from reliance on common cognitive heuristics that help people navigate their complex social world**. Thus, they are part of being human. When students are given the tools for understanding and addressing social justice inequities, their overall bias literacy, or their ability to detect their own and others’ prejudices, also increases. Addressing these topics results in greater openness and understanding and increases students’ multicultural competence.”

Supplementary reflection II

Kite and Clark, 2022: *“Students do not always have experience discussing emotional issues. To help them manage difficult conversations, students need a safe classroom environment, with clearly established ground rules for discussion; ideally, students will have a voice in creating these rules (Goldstein, 2021). Both students and instructors also must be mindful of how privilege affects classroom dynamics. This awareness includes consideration of who is in the room and who has social power.”*

Kite et al, 2021: *“Confronting others’ stereotypes and prejudices can seem daunting. Just what should you say, and how should you say it? Is it your place to speak up? Will your confrontation come with costs, such as people not liking you, or perhaps backfire so that the perpetrator spews even more offensive remarks? Bias literacy is the cornerstone of successful training workshops in work contexts that teach people to be aware of their own and others’ biases.”*

Ask yourself the following

- How might your own cultural-bound assumptions influence your interactions with students?
- How might the backgrounds and experiences of your students influence their motivation, engagement, and learning in your classroom?
- How can you modify course materials, activities, assignments, and/or exams to be more accessible to all students in your class?

(Cornell University, Inclusive teaching strategies)

3.2.

Strategies for teaching international students to boost inclusivity

- Do not let multi-active, extroverted students to dominate conversations in class or in small group discussions, but intervene with direct questions to more reserved, introverted students who can be coming from reactive cultures.
- Diversify teaching materials e.g. so that you have e.g. research articles, expert interview videos and examples in your teaching materials that are from Global South or Asia instead of only from Europe or the US. This will develop students' critical thinking skills.
- Acknowledge and admit your own biases and that you can't know all those cultures your international students come from but express your interests in learning about them instead.

- Clarify your communication.
- Set up a Q&A box on the learning platform and encourage students to ask questions there instead of sending private emails. Often the question concerns several students and not just one.
- Explain when email questions are to be used.
- Provide extra visual and oral support while presenting information. This can help a great deal students whose academic English skills are still developing.
- Write out or emphasize key words.
- Use phrases that clearly mark important information and transitions between ideas. (e.g. The most important point to remember is... So that's the first point and now let's move on to others...)
- Use paraphrases to support students in their learning and avoid abstract language.
- Use written materials to supplement classroom communication.

- Encourage students to record class sessions, especially lectures, so that they can listen to them like podcasts on their own and at their own pace.
- Give students in a one-on-one setting constructive feedback on recurring language mistakes they might make. Normally this feedback is highly appreciated by students.
- Give students a chance to reflect upon their learning at the end of the session. Allow time for a Q&A session at the end of the class or ask them to write a 1-minute paper to summarize the most important points of the class.
- Try to engage students in the class by asking them questions. Give them time to think about their response or plan a series of questions to guide their thinking. Put students ALWAYS in multicultural teams for group discussions.
- Pay attention to your own active listening skills - are you giving enough time for the students to speak? Are you expressing attentiveness through your own non-verbal cues?

- Define clear expectations for written assignments through explicit instructions incl. evaluation criteria. Students come from different cultural backgrounds with massive differences when it comes to their previous learning →they might not understand what is expected from them.
- Define formalities (due date, format, length, citations etc.)
- Explain teaching methods.
- What is expected from students regarding a lecture? Problem-based learning? Self-reflective essay?

3.3.

Learning styles and teaching styles

- How do we adapt our teaching style, or our higher education working style, in general, according to students' learning styles? Do we even ask this ourselves, in higher education, or we assume that with adult learners it doesn't matter?
- According to Burke Barbe, who developed the subject in the 1920s, together with Milone (Barbe & Milone, 1981), students' learning preferences are a combination of visual (V), auditory (A) and kinesthetic (K) channels, with a dominant preference for one of the channels. Later on, Fleming improved the VAK model by adding another channel, the reading/writing one, which is in fact a combination of visual and auditory, meaning VARK model.

Visual learners can be described by the following:

- Learn best by seeing information
- Can easily recall printed information in the form of numbers, words, phrases, or sentences
- Can easily understand and recall information presented in pictures, charts, or diagrams
- Have strong visualization skills, that involve sizes, shapes, textures, angles and dimensions and can even make "movies in their minds" of information they are reading
- Pay close attention and learn to interpret body language (facial expressions, eyes, stance).

Auditory learners are best described by the following:

- Learn best by hearing information
- Can accurately remember details of information heard in conversations or lectures
- Have strong language skills that include well-developed vocabularies and appreciation of words
- Have strong oral communication skills that enable them to carry on conversations and be articulate
- Have “finely tuned ears” and may find learning a foreign language relatively easy comparing to other types of learners.

Kinesthetic learners are those who:

- Learn best by doing things
- Learn best by using their hands (“Hands-on” learning) or by the movement of their full body
- Often need to wiggle, tap their feet, or move their legs when they sit, being sometimes labeled as “hyperactive”
- Need to „experience” things by themselves.

- You can find the type of learning styles in your class by using a simple questionnaire, labeled Learning Styles Inventory (LSI), <https://www.middlesex.mass.edu/ace/downloads/lsi.pdf>
- Although there are not strong direct connections between the learning style and students' academic performance, when teachers adapt their lectures to make room for all these preferences, students might feel more at ease, develop a better attachment to that class and thus perform better.

Teachers' styles (1)

The Grasha-Riechmann Teaching-Styles Inventory assesses several styles: Expert, Formal Authority, Personal Model, Facilitator, and Delegator. (<https://cte.smu.edu.sg/teaching-styles>)

- **The Expert teacher:** has knowledge and expertise that students need and strives to maintain status as an expert among students by displaying detailed knowledge; attempts to challenge students to enhance their competence; concentrates on transmitting information and requires that students be prepared to learn and use that information. The information, knowledge, and skills are the combined advantage of this teaching style. If overused, the display of knowledge may intimidate less experienced students. Also, the display of knowledge and skills may not always reveal their underpinnings.
- **The Formal Authority teacher:** focuses on rules and has a certain status among students because of his knowledge, and his role as a faculty member; provides positive and negative feedback; establishes learning goals and expectations and rules of conduct, providing students with a learning structure. Students concentrate on correct, acceptable, and standard methods.

Teachers' styles (2)

- **The Personal Model teacher:** believes in teaching by personal example. This professor establishes a prototype for thinking and behaviour, then oversees, guides, and directs by showing students how to do things. He or she also encourages students to observe, and then emulate the instructor's approach.
- **The Facilitator teacher:** emphasizes the personal nature of teacher-student interactions and focuses on facilitating students' learning journey; guides and directs students by asking questions, exploring options, and suggesting alternatives; encourages students to develop criteria to make informed choices; concentrates on the overall classroom goal of developing the capacity for independent action, initiative, and responsibility, while providing students with as much support and encouragement as possible.
- **The Delegator teacher:** develops students' capacity to function in an autonomous fashion. This type of educator encourages students to work on projects independently or as part of autonomous teams; is available upon request as a resource person.

All these styles have advantages and disadvantages and should be adapted to both previous cultural and professional backgrounds of students, as well as to their native preferences in terms of learning.

3.4.

Challenging scenarios and their solutions for teaching and guiding diverse students

In the following slides you'll see some real-life examples of challenging situations you can face while teaching international classes. All these examples are real. By reading them, try to think about what would be a culturally-sensitive approach to solving the situation.

You can read a clarification for what actually happened and a possible solution for sorting out the situation in some of the slide.

Racist behavior in teamwork

Student A doesn't want to work with student B in the same team and asks to be changed into another team because student B is from a completely different world/background than student A and student A has had bad experiences with a student coming from the same culture as student B. How do you solve the situation?

Guidelines to solve it:

This kind of behavior is a clear example of stereotyping, prejudicing and clearly racist behavior. A teacher should not change the student to another team but give him/her an opportunity to hopefully have a positive experience from a new student representing the culture the student has had bad experiences with. You could take the student aside and ask in person how he/she would feel if he/she was ignored, labeled due to others and whether or not the student understands how that kind of thinking is clearly stereotyping and racist.

Flirtation in emails – gender

As a female teacher you keep getting emails from a male student that have a tone that can be interpreted as sweet talking, flirtation or expression of a sexual interest.

What to do?

Guidelines to solve it:

This kind of behavior can be quite common from male students representing cultures where there are challenges in gender equality. It has to be pointed out to them very clearly that this kind of behavior is seen as inappropriate.

Sleepiness in class

A male student from Asia is falling asleep in class and it looks that during the one and a half months since he has been studying at your university, he has lost quite much weight. What can be the problem, how do you address and solve it?

Guidelines to solve it:

Tiredness, depression, losing or gaining weight within a short time frame or getting a sudden rash or plenty of pimples on one's face are some clear symptoms of culture shock that should be addressed. Male students coming from collectivist and male-dominating cultures can have very poor or even non-existing skills in meal preparation and could be eating just rice and fruits like it was the case in this situation. Intervention and guiding the student to look for help from student health care services is important. When dealing with symptoms of culture shock, maintaining a normal rhythm of the day is of great importance and it can be seen as a big mistake if the student isolates himself/herself from others to keep contact with family and friends in their home country.

The feeling of being excluded from groupwork

The working language in a project group work is English. However, the native language of the country is spoken in group meetings, breaks and free discussions. The new international student does not yet speak and understand the local language well. He/She is unable to participate in the discussion while other group members keep talking in their native language.

The student brings up this problem to you in the middle of the project work, what do you do?

Guidelines to solve it:

The feeling of belonging and exclusion should be addressed among international groups of students with examples such as the teacher answers questions in English that native students make in their native languages or that the teacher could answer the question in a third language that the student won't understand. When groupworks are instructed, the question of the communication language should be addressed from the very beginning to boost the sense of belonging.

A shouting student

I had an encounter with a student from X country. He was polite and participated in the course, but failed to hand in his final work on time. I gave him extra time, but then he handed in a text that was below par. He hadn't followed the instructions at all and the language was not very academic. He came into my office, very angry and started shouting at me that I was wrong to not pass him from this course. I tried to stay calm and explain why I couldn't pass him. He kept on yelling at me so loud that even one of my colleagues came into the room (he was male) and asked if everything was okay. That defused the situation a little, so I think I got through to him. At least he calmed down a bit and left without hitting me (I felt that was a serious threat at one point). I never heard from him since.

Guidelines to solve it:

In this kind of a situation it would be important to communicate with the student in a calm manner and to point out to him, how his communication is seen as aggressive and in no way appropriate in academia. Keep at least a desk between yourself and the student and do not try to touch the student in any way because that could easily lead to a more violent reaction.

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Authors and Contact information:

Wilfred Tchasse (Project coordinator, Kauno Kolegija, Lithuania):

wilfred.tchasse@go.kauko.lt

Petra Garnjost (IO1, htw saar, Germany) petra.garnjost@htwsaar.de Jaana

Häkli (IO2, LAB University, Finland): jaana.hakli@lab.fi

Carmen Claudia Aruștei (IO3, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University, Romania)

carmen.arustei@feaa.uaic.ro

Elena de Prada (Train the trainers and dissemination activities,

Universidade de Vigo, Spain) edeprada@uvigo.es

Blog: <https://globdives.blogspot.com/>

**ALEXANDRU IOAN CUZA
UNIVERSITY of IAȘI**

**KAUNO
KOLEGIJA**

**LAB University of
Applied Sciences**

Universida_{de}Vigo

htw saar

Diversity is a *fact*.
Inclusion is an *act*.

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